

QUIZ**LAST NAME: WRIGHT****FIRST NAME: JENNY****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: P6****INSTRUCTOR: PR. CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references.The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access).The author used the following software: MS Word 2016 on Windows 10.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is the difference between primary and secondary sources?**
 - Primary sources are more reliable than secondary sources.
 - Primary sources are first-hand evidence while secondary sources are (secondary) analysis of primary sources.¹**
 - Primary sources answer the first research question while secondary sources answer the second research question.
 - Secondary sources are used if there are insufficient primary sources.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations – Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 24.

2. **Which research paradigm is most commonly used by advocates and is conducted for the purpose of prompting social change and/or political reform?**
- Pragmatism
 - Social constructivism
 - Critical theory²**
 - Postpositivism
3. **Which of the below does not require a source citation?**
- A common knowledge, i.e. a widely accepted statement.³**
 - A short quote, i.e. a statement within quotation marks.
 - A long quote, i.e. an indented statement in a separate paragraph.
 - A paraphrase, i.e. a statement rephrased in your own words.
4. **Which qualitative research tradition mainly uses information derived from storytelling?**
- Hermeneutics.
 - Grounded theory.
 - Ethnography.
 - Narrative inquiry.⁴**

² Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 9.

³ EUCLID, ACA-401: Coursepack (Euclid University, 2015): 32, accessed September 23, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 11.

5. **What is a hypothesis?**
- A statement that contradicts the thesis statement.
 - A type of research method.
 - A preliminary answer to a research question.⁵**
 - A group of research participants.
6. **What type of chart shows the proportion of a single variable for a series of cases?**
- Pie chart.⁶**
 - Image chart.
 - Bar chart.
 - Area chart.
7. **Observation, critical incidents, focus group, and document review all are examples of what?**
- Ethical considerations.
 - Purposive sampling.
 - Conceptual frameworks.
 - Qualitative data collection.⁷**

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 21.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 66.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 217.

8. Which is **not** an important element of a solid argument?
- A calculation of the total number of sources used.⁸
 - Evidence supporting the argument.
 - A pre-emptive defense to critique or alternative views.
 - A warrant that establishes the relevance of the claim(s).
9. What does the triangulation of data collection methods involve?
- Illustrating the data collection in a triangular chart.
 - Ensuring 3 researchers are involved in the data collection.
 - Combining multiple methods to verify evidence.⁹
 - Using the same research participant(s) for all 3 parts of a study.
10. Three of these purposeful sampling strategies are direct opposite of each other (antonyms), while one option includes two similar strategies (synonyms). Which are synonyms?
- Typical case sampling and deviant case sampling.
 - Snowball sampling and chain sampling.¹⁰
 - Maximum variation sampling and homogenous sampling.
 - Random sampling and criterion sampling.

⁸ Turabian, A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 37.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, 99.

¹⁰ Ibid., Appendix C.

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Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.